

DEVELOPMENT OF DRILLING TECHNOLOGY WITH HYDRAULIC MOTORS IN SALT BLOOD CONDITIONS.

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Abstract: *Improving the efficiency of deep wells and fairways in oilfields with salt rock deposits by developing and implementing drilling techniques and technologies through hydraulic drilling motors (HDM).*

The results of research on the creation of new technical tools and technologies for drilling side-by-side and multilateral wells with small-diameter screw well engines are presented. Such the wells different different deflector devices using of drilling enough a lot methods known. This of methods disadvantages between them done in raising addition technical from tools use, extra respectively addition turn off need for operations (SPO). giving birth enters

We main of the well extended of the plot from the edge a lot bilaterally the wells of drilling new without a dagger method offer we did and We patented it stable in rocks a lot edged the wells reliable drilling enable gives their the number shorten through from work exit the time reduces as well. filtering surfaces addition branches with increase through a lot edged of the well come in came productive layers oil to get increases. DR type variable using angular PDM patented method using five network the well successful drilled.

Pripjat in depth oil mines location geological conditions , water warehouses types and fertile in horizons of the sexes features small diameter bits with drilling during harvest has been open through the hole efficient use enable gives the well filter zone With that together , embedded diamond bits such drilling conditions the most efficient is , moment and rotation speed increase Demand does Small diameter PDM - types D-76 4/5.40 and DR-95 5/6.50 moment increase for they are suitable respectively new characters designation with undirected collection to the scheme according to split : 2D-76 4/5.80 and 2DR-95 5/6.100. Washing at SOI-250 of liquid flow of speed one different in values determined assembled two sectional PDM moments maximum efficiency mode standard one partial of engines similar 1.7 of the indicators to increased 1.8 times , light (by 2-3 pp)) maximum efficiency increase Har different size embedded diamond bit 2D-76 4/5.80 and 2DR-95 5/6.100 two sectional screw the well engines using side of roads open the ends drilling according to work developed technology his own high efficiency showed . Mechanic penetration level 2.8 - 4.6 times increased of wells strength supply, circulation loss and another kind of of complications prevention to get separately requirements to put was determined. This problems solution to do for special devices - colmatators using permeable layers in opening the well mandatory hydrodynamic colmatization to do technology work released and done increased Drilling of liquid of loss intensity prevention get or reduce for drilling tool as drilling tool as used, circulation or into the turbine BHA incoming reactive stuck stay ejection type of devices work developed constructions republic patents with protected . Belarus and Russia Federation.

Salty gunders mines has been Pripyat in depth oil in the mines deep the wells drilling according to work developed technologies current reach according to technical and economic justification results given. Economical of efficiency calculations RD 39-0148052-547-87 " Oil and gas wells in construction new equipment, inventions and rationalization from suggestions of use economic efficiency to determine temporary method , M., VNIIOENG, 1988. ". Calculation algorithm standard trip time, drilling tools to work drop off for preparation final and helper from work to use mean holds.

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